

METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF PHYSICS TEACHERS BASED ON QUALIMETRIC INDICATORS

A.K. Fayzullayev

Gulistan State University PhD student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15766113>

Abstract. *This article presents a methodology for assessing the pedagogical competence of physics teachers based on qualimetric indicators. In addition, the article identifies the main components of assessing a teacher's pedagogical competence and develops assessment mechanisms using qualimetric indicators such as teacher knowledge and the use of didactic, methodological, information and communication and innovative technologies, and a model for assessing pedagogical competence based on these qualimetric indicators is developed.*

Keywords: *method, didactics, qualimetry, competence, methodology, pedagogical qualimetry, didactic competence, methodological competence, communicative competence, innovative approach, expert assessment, portfolio analysis, digital diagnostics, 360-degree assessment.*

Introduction

In the modern education system, the professional training of a teacher, his pedagogical competence, is one of the main criteria for the quality of education. Physics is distinguished from other disciplines by its theoretical depth and experimental features. Therefore, a scientifically based methodological approach is necessary for an effective and accurate assessment of the competence of future physics teachers. Qualimetry is one of the main tools in this regard, which allows assessing competence through quantitative indicators.

To date, State educational standards, accreditation criteria and requirements for rating assessment of pedagogical activities are being further improved based on the experience of foreign developed countries. This is evidence of the increasing attention paid to the qualitative assessment of teachers' pedagogical and professional competence. Qualimetric approaches provide an opportunity to diagnose the pedagogical and professional competence of a teacher, analyze the quality and effectiveness of teaching.

We will focus on the scientific views of some prominent scientists who have conducted research on the methodology for assessing teachers' pedagogical competence based on qualimetric indicators and its improvement, and who have contributed to the creation of its methodological foundations.

According to V.V. Kraevsky, competence is not only knowledge, but also the readiness to apply it in real pedagogical situations. According to the scientist, it is necessary to analyze the professional competence of a teacher and evaluate it on the basis of methodological, communicative, organizational and reflexive components. He believes that these components can be assessed using qualimetric criteria.

I.A. Zimnyaya interprets the professional competence of a teacher as an integration of knowledge, skills, qualifications, cultural values, and experience. In her research, the scientist developed a methodology for determining the levels of personal, communicative, and professional

assessment through a qualimetric approach. This approach is especially relevant in the training of future teachers.

In A.V. Khutorskoy's research, a mechanism for assessing competencies used in pedagogical activity based on qualimetric criteria and indicators has been developed. Using the example of a physics teacher, he distinguishes subject-related, methodological, and technological competencies, and relies on qualimetric indicators to measure them.

The analysis of scientific research shows that improving the methodological foundations of pedagogical qualimetry is of great importance: the creation of methodological foundations for assessing the quality of personnel in the social and economic development of society, the training of future teachers in higher educational institutions. There are the following conceptual foundations of pedagogical qualimetry.

Today, in the conditions of increased demand for education and science, a physics teacher is required not only to have a deep knowledge of his subject, but also to equip it pedagogically and didactically, to use modern pedagogical technologies in teaching science, and to be able to increase students' interest in science. Innovative approaches to the formation of such skills in physics teachers and the assessment of their activities are not enough. The qualitative approach to pedagogy provides an opportunity to systematically and objectively analyze these qualities based on certain pedagogical criteria.

Qualimetric assessment in the pedagogical process is a methodology for assessing and analyzing educational quality indicators based on mathematical expression. Through this approach to assessing educational quality, pedagogical processes (for example, teacher competence) are evaluated based on specific criteria.

Let's move on to the methodological foundations of qualitative assessment of the pedagogical process.

Theoretically, the scientific basis for qualitative assessment of the quality of education is psychology, pedagogy, and statistics. Methodologically, it is the methods and techniques used for qualitative assessment. It is important to clarify and improve qualitative indicators for assessing the pedagogical competence of teachers.

Qualimetric indicators for assessing the pedagogical competence of a physics teacher:

1. Didactic competence
2. Methodological competence
3. ICT competence
4. Communicative competence
5. Innovative approach competence

The didactic competency indicator assesses the teacher's ability to explain a topic scientifically, formulate a topic plan, and design a topic based on that plan. The assessment of this indicator is based on tests, questionnaires, interviews, and lesson plans.

The methodological competency indicator assesses the teacher's ability to conduct physics experiments and use modern methods of explaining them to students, as well as the ability to use interactive methods appropriate to the subject. The basis for evaluating a teacher according to this indicator is practical processes and methodological developments.

The ICT competency indicator assesses the effectiveness of a teacher's effective use of virtual laboratories and simulations in teaching students relevant laboratory work in physics. It is recommended to use the control work and observation method to assess this indicator.

When assessing the **communicative competence indicator**, the culture of communication with students during the lesson and the level of aesthetic culture are assessed.

We will focus on the methods and evaluation technology for evaluating physics teachers based on qualitative indicators.

The innovative approach competency indicator assesses the level of readiness for the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies into educational practice and continuous professional pedagogical development.

Expert assessment - this assessment of the teacher's pedagogical competence is carried out by an experienced teacher and methodologist. This assessment is carried out on the basis of the didactic, methodological, ICT and communicative indicators of the physics teacher.

Self-assessment - in which the teacher assesses his or her own pedagogical competence. This process is based on the students' understanding of the subject and the quality of education.

Portfolio analysis - this evaluates the physics teacher's educational achievements, lesson plans, lesson projects and video lessons.

Digital diagnostics are carried out through testing or other forms of assessment using a specific electronic assessment platform.

360-degree evaluation - this is a type of comprehensive evaluation, in which the teacher, students, methodologists, team, and other representatives of the educational organization are involved.

It is natural to ask what is the importance of assessing a teacher's pedagogical competence based on qualimetric indicators.

In this:

accuracy and objectivity in assessing a teacher's pedagogical abilities and professional qualities;

the teacher has the opportunity to improve their professional quality and develop;

the emergence of requirements for a quality approach in the training of future teachers;

It creates opportunities such as the emergence of the opportunity for each teacher to determine their own trajectory of work on themselves.

Based on the ideas presented in our article, we recommend a qualitative assessment model of the pedagogical competence of a future physics teacher (see Figure 1). The model for assessing the pedagogical competence of future physics teachers is divided into two parts. The theoretical part assesses the level of knowledge of the teacher of the law on education, the main categories of pedagogy, the content of the pedagogical process, didactics and its goals and objectives, the concept of education, types and forms of education, types of assessment of educational results, the educational process and its content, the history of pedagogy, educational principles, pedagogical technology, methodology of teaching science, teaching methods and techniques, types of lessons and communicative pedagogy.

In the practical part, knowledge such as systematization of educational and upbringing work, use of modern pedagogical and ICT technologies in the teaching process, self-analysis, self-professional development, ability to exert pedagogical influence, and knowledge of the technology of continuous monitoring of student knowledge assessment are assessed.

The indicators for assessing the pedagogical competence of future physics teachers developed on the basis of this model are expressed in clear criteria and indicators, and assessment mechanisms are developed. The application of the model to the educational process and its

management allows future physics teachers to analyze and evaluate their professional preparation and determine individual areas of work in their field.

Overall, the model presented in this article serves as an effective assessment tool for developing the pedagogical and professional skills of physics teachers, and it is important for improving the quality of education and monitoring teacher performance.

Figure 1. Qualimetric assessment model for the pedagogical competence of physics teachers.

REFERENCES

1. Краевский В.В. Методология педагогики: предмет и структура. – М.: Исследовательский центр проблем качества подготовки специалистов, 2001. – 72 с.
2. Краевский В.В. Общие основы педагогики: учебное пособие для студентов педвузов. – М.: Академия, 2003. – 240 с.
3. Зимняя И.А. Ключевые компетенции – новая парадигма результата образования. – М.: Исследовательский центр проблем качества подготовки специалистов, 2004. – 36 с.

4. Хуторской А.В. Компетентностный подход в образовании: методология, теория, технология. – М.: Изд-во ИИТО РАО, 2005. – 240 с.
5. Хуторской А.В. Проектирование результатов образования: компетенции, компетентности, стандарты. – М.: Эврика, 2008. – 320 с.
6. Fayzullayev A.K. Pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasalarida bo'lajak mutaxassislarni kvalimetrik ko'rsatkichlarini baholash texnologiyasi. Ta'lim, fan va innovatsiya ma'naviy-marifiy, ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali 2023-yil. Noyabr. 193-195 betlar.
7. Fayzullayev A.K. Pedagogik kvalimetriya ko'rsatkichlari asosida o'qituvchilarning kasbiy mahoratini aniqlash, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi Urganch davlat universiteti. Ilm sarchashmasi. Ilmiy-nazariy metodik jurnal. 2023-yil. Dekabr. 78-80 betlar.